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First **R**ecord of *Hoplictis* (Carnivora, Mustelidae) in East Asia from the Halamagai and Kekemaideng Formations, Ulungur **R**iver **A**rea, Xinjiang, Northwest China

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24
25 **Abstract:** We report for the first time, unequivocal remains of medium to large sized mustelids
26 from the middle Miocene Halamagai and Kekemaideng formations in Ulungur River area,
27 Xinjiang, north-western China. These new fossils are referred to the hypercarnivorous mustelid
28 *Hoplictis* Ginsburg, 1961, which denote the first record of the genus in East Asia. We define
29 *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp., for the mustelid from Tieersihabahe (Halamagai Fm.), which represents the
30 smallest species of the genus. It is a primitive form, closer to *H. florigencei* and *H. noueli* than to *H.*
31 *anatolicus* and the later, larger and more derived *Hoplictis* from Europe and North America. The
32 large mandible without teeth from Duolebulejin (Kekemaideng Fm.) is assigned to *Hoplictis* cf.
33 *helbingi*, and it presumably represents the first record of *H. helbingi* outside Western Europe.
34 Therefore, the occurrence in East Asia of these two species of *Hoplictis*, greatly expands the
35 known distribution and diversity of the genus, and supports a Palaearctic Neogene dispersal event
36 of carnivorans between Europe and Asia during the late Shanwangian – early Tunggurian
37 equivalent to MN5–6 in Europe, and indication another dispersal event from Europe to North
38 America, through Northwest China during the late Tunggurian, equivalent to MN7–8 in Europe.

39
40 **Key words:** Mustelidae, Miocene, *Hoplictis*, *Ischyriactis*, Halamagai, Kekemaideng

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43
44 **1 Introduction**

46 Mustelids represent the largest living family of carnivorans and possesses an abundant fossil record
47 in the early and middle Miocene of Europe and North America (e.g. Blainville 1842; Filhol 1872;
48 Depéret 1892; Mayet 1908; Viret 1933, 1951; Helbing 1928, 1930, 1936; Dehm 1950; Ginsburg 1961,
49 1999, 2002; Roth 1989; Ginsburg and Morales 1992; Baskin 1998, 2005, 2017; Nagel et al., 2009;
50 Peigné 2012; Valenciano et al., 2016, 2018). However, our understanding of Asiatic forms is more
51 limited (Babbitt 1999, Peigné et al., 2006), despite Asia being located between the two continents. Early
52 Miocene mustelid remains from Asia are poorly documented (Peigné et al., 2006). They include
53 *Mustela* sp. and *Proputorius* from Xiejia and Sihong Faunas in China (Qiu and Qiu 1995; Hunt 1996),
54 the leptarctine Mustelidae *Kinometaxia guangpui* Wang et al., 2004, from Danghe (Tabenbuluk) area of
55 the northern Tibetan Plateau (Wang et al., 2004), an unidentified small mustelid from DM16 locality in
56 Damiao, Inner Mongolia (Zhang et al., 2011), and a P4 of another unidentified small mustelid from
57 Kazakhstan (Kordikova et al., 2000: fig. 4e, f). The record of these forms in China during the middle
58 Miocene is more complete. Mustelids from the Tunggur Fm in Inner Mongolia, of middle Miocene age,
59 yield a better understanding of the family and the entire order (Qiu et al., 2013a and references herein).
60 The local fauna of carnivores includes the immigrant North American mustelids *Leptarcus*
61 *neimenguensis* Zhai, 1964, and *Sthenictis neimenguensis* Tseng et al., 2009, as well as *Melodon?* sp.
62 (Colbert 1939). In Damiao, Tunggurian DM01 locality, several mustelids are present, but no details
63 were published by Zhang et al. (2011). The middle Miocene Halamagai Fm, located in northwest China,
64 is an additional significant formation in the country. It has yielded an interesting and rich assemblage of
65 carnivorans (Wang et al., 1998; Bi et al., 1999; Ye et al., 2001a, b; Wu et al., 2003; Ye et al., 2005; Qiu
66 et al., 2013b; Jiangzuo et al., 2018), comprising the ailurids *Alopecocyon goeriachensis* (Toula, 1884)
67 and *Simocyon* sp., the amphicyonids *Amphicyon ulungurensis* Qi, 1989, *Gobicyon zhegallo* Gabunia,
68 1981, *Cynelos* cf. *bohemicus* Schlosser, 1899, *Cynelos* aff. *helbingi* Dehm, 1950, and cf. *Cynelos* sp.,
69 the nimravid *Nimravus* sp., the felid *Pseudaelurus cuspidatus* Wang et al., 1998, as well as the hyaenids
70 *Tungurictis spocki* Colbert, 1939, *Protictitherium intermedium* Schmidt-Kittler, 1976, *Protictitherium*
71 sp., and *Thalassictis chinjiensis* (Pilgrim, 1932). The single mustelid described from Halamagai is a
72 fragmentary mandible of a juvenile with deciduous teeth and premolar germs reported by Wang et al.
73 (1998) as *Oligobunis?* sp., which could represent the first oligobunine mustelid found in the Old world.
74 Unfortunately, more material is needed to corroborate this important find. Neither the mustelids nor the
75 other carnivoran remains from Kekemaideng Fm have been described.

76 The newly discovered fossil specimens reported herein from the middle Miocene of China are
77 referred to the genus *Hoplictis* Ginsburg, 1961. This genus represents a hypercarnivorous mustelid
78 recorded from the early Miocene to the early late Miocene of the Northern Hemisphere (Mayet 1908;
79 Helbing 1930; Viret 1951; Bryant 1968; Crusafont-Pairó 1972; Edwards 1976; Gabunia 1973; Schmidt-
80 Kittler 1976; Roth 1989; Baskin 1998, 2005; Pickford et al., 2000). Six species has been attributed to it:
81 *Hoplictis florancei* (Mayet, 1908), from Pontlevoy-Thenay (type locality), France, early middle
82 Miocene, MN5 (European Neogene Land Mammals Ages), and from Erkertshofen 2, Germany, late
83 early Miocene (MN4) (Roth 1989); *Hoplictis noueli* (Mayet, 1908) from Artenay, France, (MN4);
84 *Hoplictis anatolicus* (Schmidt-Kittler, 1976) from Çandır (type locality), Paşalar, and Mordogan in
85 Turkey (MN5–6) (Gürbüz 1992; Kaya et al., 2003; Nagel 2003), and from Belometchetskaya in Belarus
86 (MN6) (Gabunia 1973; Pickford et al., 2000); *Hoplictis helbingi* (Viret, 1951) from La Grive (type
87 locality, MN7–8, France) and Castell de Barberà, Spain, early late Miocene (MN9) (Crusafont-Pairó
88 1972); *Hoplictis?* *petteri* Crusafont-Pairó, 1972 from Can Llobateres I, Spain (MN9); and *Hoplictis*
89 (= *Beckia*) *grangerensis* (Bryant, 1968) in North America during the late Clarendonian (North American
90 Land Mammal Ages, c. MN9–10) both in Granger Clay Pit, Washington, and in the locality V6107 in
91 Contra Costa Group, Los Angeles, (Edwards 1976). Furthermore, it is present in Love Bone Bed,
92 Florida as *Hoplictis* sp. (Baskin 2005). In spite of this great diversity, the available material is scarce
93 and comprises predominantly mandibular remains and isolated lower teeth, with the exception of an M1
94 of *H. noueli* from Artenay (Helbing 1930, fig. 3), a P4 of *H. helbingi* from La Grive (Viret 1951, pl. II,
95 fig. 13), and quite a complete skull with mandibles and some postcranial remains of *H. anatolicus* from
96 Çandır (Schmidt-Kittler 1976, fig. 20-24, pl. IA, B).

97 The aim of this work is to describe some of the unpublished remains of large mustelids from the
 98 Halamagai and Kekemaideng formations, comparing them with small to large mustelids from the late
 99 Oligocene to late Miocene of Asia, Europe, North America and Africa.

101 2 Localities and Formations

103 Ulungur River area in Northern Junggar Basin (location see Fig. 1) is one of the most important fossil
 104 site assemblages in western China, with deposits ranging in age from the late Eocene to the late
 105 Miocene. The middle Miocene Halamagai Fm has already produced abundant Carnivora, so far
 106 including five to seven species of amphicyonids, two species of ailurids, one species of mustelid, three
 107 species of hyaenids, one species of felid and one possible species of nimravid (Qi 1989; Wang et al.,
 108 1998, Jiangzuo et al., 2018). The base of the formation was estimated to be 17 Ma on the basis of
 109 palaeomagnetic correlation (Ye et al., 2012), therefore the main part of the Halamagai Fm corresponds
 110 to the late Shanwangian – early Tunggurian or MN5–6 in Europe (Qiu et al., 2013a). The Kekemaideng
 111 Fm, which overlies the Halamagai Fm is thought to be late Tunggurian in age, equivalent to MN7–8 in
 112 Europe (Ye et al., 2012).

114 3 Material and Methods

116 The materials were collected by Sijian Xu and Jie Ye in 2017. All the material of *Hoplictis* from
 117 China studied here is housed in the IVPP. For comparison we studied the original fossils of *Namibictis*
 118 *senuti* Morales et al., 1998 from Arrisdrift, early-middle Miocene of Namibia (Morales et al., 1998,
 119 2003) housed at the Museum of the Geological Survey of Namibia; *Iberictis azanzae* Ginsburg and
 120 Morales, 1992 from Artesilla, Spain, early Miocene, MN4 (Ginsburg and Morales 1992; Valenciano et
 121 al., 2018) housed at MPZ; *Iberictis buloti* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992 from els Casots, Spain, early
 122 Miocene, MN4 (Valenciano et al., 2018) housed at ICP; *Laphictis mustelinus* (Viret, 1933), from Can
 123 Mata 1 (Villalta Comella and Crusafont Pairó 1943; Petter 1963), Spain, middle Miocene MN7–8,
 124 housed at ICP; *Hoplictis helbingi* from Castell de Barberà (Crusafont-Pairó 1972), Spain, early late
 125 Miocene, MN9, housed at ICP; *Eomellivora fricki* (= *Hoplictis petteri*) from Can Llobateres I
 126 (Crusafont-Pairó 1972), Spain MN9, housed at ICP. We also studied *Martes munki* Roger, 1900 from
 127 La Grive, France, MN7–8, and *Martes burdigaliensis* Beaumont, 1974 from Vieux-Collonges, France,
 128 MN5 by casts housed at MNCN and a cast of *Hoplictis* (= *Beckia*) *grangerensis* (Bryant, 1968) from
 129 Granger Clay Pit, North America housed at AMNH. We further inspected photographs of *Dehmictis*
 130 *vorax* (Dehm, 1950) from Wintershof-West, early Miocene, MN3, Germany housed at BSPG; *Martes*
 131 *sansaniensis* (Lartet, 1851) and *Ischyriictis zibethoides* (Blainville, 1842) from Sansan, France, middle
 132 Miocene, MN6, such as *Hoplictis noueli* from Artenay, France, early Miocene, MN4, housed at NMB
 133 and MNHN, the early-middle Miocene *Hoplictis floraencei* from Erkerthshofen 2, Germany, late early
 134 Miocene MN4, and Pontlevoy-Thenay, France, early middle Miocene, MN5 housed at BSPG and
 135 MNHN respectively; *Hoplictis anatolicus* from Çandır, Turkey, middle Miocene, MN6 housed at
 136 BSPG; and *Hoplictis helbingi* from La Grive, France, MN7–8, housed at FSL.

137 Dental nomenclature follows Ginsburg (1999) and Smith and Dodson (2003). Measurements were
 138 made with digital calipers accurate to 0.02 mm.

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 140 *Institutional abbreviations.* AD, Arrisdrift collection, Museum of the Geological Survey of Namibia,
 141 Windhoek, Namibia; BSPG, Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontologie und Geologie, Munich,
 142 Germany; FSL, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1; [GSI, Geological Survey of India, Kolkata, India](#);
 143 MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales Madrid, Spain; MNHN: Muséum national d'Histoire
 144 naturelle, Paris, France; MPZ, collection of the former Museo Paleontológico de la Universidad de
 145 Zaragoza, currently housed at the Museo de Ciencias Naturales Universidad de Zaragoza, Zaragoza,
 146 Spain; NMB, Naturhistorisches Museum Basel, Switzerland; ICP, Institut Català de Paleontologia
 147 Miquel Crusafont, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain; IPS, collections from the ICP (formerly
 148 'Institut de Paleontologia de Sabadell'); V, collections of vertebrates housed at IVPP (Institute of
 149 Vertebrate Paleontology and Paleoanthropology), Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China.

4 Systematic Palaeontology

Order Carnivora Bowdich, 1821

Suborder Caniformia Kretzoi, 1943

Indraorder Arctoidea Flower, 1869

Superfamily Musteloidea Fischer, 1817

Family Mustelidae Fischer, 1817

Genus *Hoplictis* Ginsburg, 1961

Type species. *Hoplictis florancei* (Mayet, 1908) from Pontlevoy-Thenay, France, early middle Miocene (MN5).

Referred species and type localities. *Hoplictis noueli* (Mayet, 1908) from Artenay (MN4, France), *Hoplictis anatolicus* (Schmidt-Kittler, 1976) from Çandir (MN6, Turkey), *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp. (Tieersihabahe, Halamagai Fm., c. MN5–6, China);

Hoplictis helbingi (Viret, 1951) from La Grive (MN7–8, France) and *Hoplictis grangerensis* (Bryant, 1968) from Granger Clay Pit (Clarendonian, USA).

Original diagnosis. Modified from Ginsburg and Morales (1992), and Ginsburg (1999). Mustelid close to *Ischyrictis* but with a more hypercarnivorous tendency, with lingual part of M1 reduced, m1 slightly higher, narrower, and without metaconid and entoconid.

Emended diagnosis. Hypercarnivorous mustelid with long P4 with reduced protocone; M1 with metacone and lingual platform reduced; deep mandibular corpus; p4 high with posterior accessory cuspid; m1 relatively high, with metaconid reduced or absent, and slender talonid with a dominant hypoconid imbricated toward the protoconid and without entoconid.

Hoplictis baihu n. sp.

Figures 2A–F, 4A–C, 5A–C, Table 1

Derivation of name. Named in honour to the holy beast Baihu (Bái Hǔ in Chinese), a white tiger from the traditional Chinese culture, which is considered to be the symbol of the West, in accordance of the West part of China in where *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp. was found and in relation to its hypercarnivorous felid-like m1.

Holotype. V24986, partial left hemimandible with c and p2 alveolus, and complete p3–m2.

Referred material. V25014, partial left hemimandible with p2, broken p3, p4 and a broken m1.

Type locality. Tieersihabahe, Halamagai Fm., [late Shanwangian or early Tunggurian \(MN5-6\)](#), (China).

Diagnosis. Small species of *Hoplictis* with short p2, m1 protoconid higher than paraconid, with reduced metaconid, and weak cingulid, and much reduced m2.

Differential diagnosis. Differs from *Hoplictis florancei*, *Hoplictis noueli*, ~~*Hoplictis florancei*~~, *Hoplictis anatolicus*, *Hoplictis helbingi* and *Hoplictis grangerensis* by its smaller dimensions. It differs from *Hoplictis florancei*, *Hoplictis noueli* and *Hoplictis anatolicus* in the shorter p2, the lesser development of the p4 distal accessory cuspid, and in the weaker m1 cingulid. It differs from *Hoplictis florancei* in the presence of m1 metaconid. It differs from *Hoplictis anatolicus* in the slender p2 and p3, in the reduced m1 metaconid, in the relatively broader m1 talonid, and in the much more reduced m2. Additionally, it differs from *Hoplictis helbingi* and *Hoplictis grangerensis* in the shorter m1 paraconid, in the presence of m1 metaconid, in the relatively broader m1 talonid and in the reduced m2.

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 3 | 202 *Description.* V24986 is a fragmentary left hemimandible with p3–m2 (Fig. 2A–C). It is deep and
 4 203 massively built. The depth of the horizontal ramus is nearly uniform in the preserved part. The
 5 204 symphysis is elongated, its medial surface is rugose, and the attachment of the fibrocartilage pad is
 6 205 more conspicuous in the dorsal area of the symphysis. The distal part of the symphysis reaches the
 7 206 middle part of the p3. Three mental foramina are present in the anterior part of horizontal ramus. The
 8 207 anterior one is the smallest and is located at the caudal edge of the root of the canine. The middle one is
 9 208 the largest and is located at the boundary between the p2 and the p3. The caudal one is located at the
 10 209 distal part of the p3. The masseteric fossa is deep and its rostral edge reaches the boundary between the
 11 210 m1 and the m2. The alveoli for i1–i3 and canine are present (Fig. 2C). The canine, relatively large
 12 211 (measurements at the base 6.22 x 4.52 mm) and the p2 are broken at the most basal level of the crown.
 13 212 The p1 is absent (Fig. 2C). The p2 is double-rooted and oriented slightly distolingually. The larger distal
 14 213 root indicates that the tooth is distally broadened. The p3 is high and sharp. Buccally, the mesial cristid
 15 214 is nearly straight whereas the distal cristid is slightly concave. The widest part of the tooth lies in the
 16 215 posterior area. No accessory cuspids are present, but there is a small bulge in the base of the distal
 17 216 cristid. The p4 is mesiodistally enlarged in relation to the other premolars, and widened distally as is the
 18 217 cases in the p2–3. It has a similar height to that of the p3 and both teeth are probably higher than the m1
 19 218 paraconid. A tiny mesial cingulid cusp is present at the mesial corner of the p4. A distinct distal
 20 219 accessory cuspid is also present. It is located buccally at the distal cristid of the main cuspid. The distal
 21 220 cingulid forms a short shelf. The m1 is relatively high, and its protoconid is manifestly higher than the
 22 221 paraconid and the main cuspids of the p3 and the p4. The width across the trigonid is distinctly greater
 23 222 than that across the talonid. The paraconid is rather elongated and slightly lingually turned. The lingual
 24 223 wall between the paraconid and the protoconid is concave. The protoconid leans slightly distally, with
 25 224 the distal slope of the protoconid rather steep. There is a large wear facet in the occlusal area of both
 26 225 paraconid and protoconid. The metaconid is very small, worn, and confined at the distolingual slope of
 27 226 the protoconid. The talonid is relatively short. The hypoconid is low. It is located buccally on the
 28 227 talonid and its tip is imbricated towards the protoconid (Fig. 2A–C). The hypoconulid is indistinct and
 29 228 the entoconid is absent. The m2 is **much**very reduced. It is a tiny button-like tooth. The length and width
 30 229 are similar. No cuspid can be identified in the crown.

31 | 230 V25014 is a horizontal ramus of a left hemimandible with p2–4 and the mesial part of the m1 (Fig.
 32 231 2D–F). The presence or absence of the p1 cannot be determined on the available material. However the
 33 232 presence a concavity with a subcircular edge in the place in which should be a p1 (Fig. 2F), could
 34 233 suggest that there may have been one and lost, being filled by mandibular bone while the mustelid was
 35 234 alive. The mandibular corpus is slightly smaller than that of V24986 but similar in overall morphology.
 36 235 Two mental foramina are present in the buccal side of the mandible. The mesial one is larger and
 37 236 located at the mesial part of the p2, whereas the distal one is smaller and located at the distal part of the
 38 237 p3. The symphysis is less rugose than that of V24986, and the distal part of the symphysis is less
 39 238 extended, only reaching the boundary between the p2 and the p3. The p2 is relatively elongated in
 40 239 relation to the p3. Neither accessory cuspids nor cingulids are present. The cuspid is broken at its apex.
 41 240 This cuspid is located at the mesial part of the tooth. The distal area of the premolar is widened. The p3
 42 241 is broken and less broad that of V24986. The p4 is morphologically close to that of V24986, but it is
 43 242 narrower distally and has a more centrally located distal accessory cuspid. Only the lingual part of the
 44 243 m1 paraconid and protoconid are preserved.

45 244
46 245 *Hoplictis helbingi* (Viret, 1951)

47 246 1892 *Aelurogale intermedia* Depéret, A.M.L, t.V, pl. I, fig. 3.

48 247 1951 *Ischyricteis helbingi* Viret, p. 52, pl. II, fig. 12a-c, 13a-b.

49 248 1972 *Ischyricteis (Hoplictis) helbingi* Crusafont-Pairó, p. 254, pl. I, fig. 1a-b.

50 249
51 250 *Lectotype.* Designated herein, a right m1 (1293) figured by Viret (1951, pl. II, fig. 12a-c) from La
 52 251 Grive (MN7–8, France).

53 252
54 253 *Other localities.* Castell de Barberà, Vallès-Penedès Basin, Spain (MN9) (Crusafont-Pairó 1972).
 55 254

255 *Diagnosis.* Designated herein. Large species of *Hoplictis* with long P4 with reduced protocone; p4
 256 alveolus distally widened; long and slender m1, without metaconid, compressed talonid in length and
 257 width, and marked lingual entocristid; oval m2 alveolus.

258
 259 *Hoplictis* cf. *helbingi*

260 Figures 2G–I, 4J–K, Table 1

261
 262 *Material.* V24988, edentulous right hemimandible.

263 *Locality.* Duolebulejin, Fm. Kekemaideng (c. [late Tunggurian](#), MN7–8, China).

264 *Description.* Large hemimandible (Fig. 2G–I) with a relatively deep horizontal ramus, and more
 265 massive than V24986. It gets deeper distally, and the depth behind the m1 is significantly greater than
 266 that behind the p2. The mesial part of the mandible is missing including part of the symphysis, the
 267 canine and p1. The distolingual area of the symphysis extends posteriorly to the middle part of the p2.
 268 There is only one large mental foramen present between the p2 and the p3. The masseteric fossa is deep
 269 and extends to the m2. All teeth are missing (excluding a small portion of the m1) and the alveoli of p2–
 270 4 and m2 are preserved (Fig. 2I). Judging from alveoli, the p2–p4 are massive. In all three premolars,
 271 the distal root is larger than the mesial one, suggesting that these teeth are distally widened. We cannot
 272 assert the presence or absence of the p1, but judging for the preserved area near the mesial part of the
 273 p2, it could be lost. The p2 is mesiobuccally and distolingually rotated, whereas the p3 and the p4 are
 274 nearly parallel to the sagittal plane. The m1 is broken at the most basal area of the crown. The mesial
 275 root is similar in size to the distal one. The overall morphology of the m1 judging from the alveoli
 276 indicates that it is an elongated and slender molar (Fig. 2I). The lingual wall is concave and the buccal
 277 one is convex. It preserves the most distal area of the protoconid. The talonid is not buccolingually
 278 enlarged. The m2 is represented by a single oval alveolus.

280 5 Comparison and Discussion

281
 282 The systematic position of *Hoplictis* has been controversial and intricate, due to the scarce available
 283 material of the genus, and partly because of its similarities with *Ischyriactis* Helbing, 1930. Initially, the
 284 first remains of *Hoplictis* from Pontlevoy-Thenay, early middle Miocene (MN5) were described as a
 285 mutation of *Trochictis zibethoides*, sp. mut. *florancei* Mayet, 1908, and similarly a hemimandible from
 286 Artenay, late early Miocene (MN4) was described as a mutation of *Trochictis zibethoides*, sp. mut.
 287 *noueli* Mayet, 1908. This author, considered the small differences found between these new forms and
 288 the large *Trochictis zibethoides* (Blainville, 1842) from Sansan, middle Miocene (MN6) —defined
 289 initially as *Viverra zibethoides* Blainville, 1842— were not enough to create new species. However,
 290 Helbing (1930) established the monospecific genus *Ischyriactis* for *Trochictis zibethoides* from Sansan
 291 and placed in this new genus the latter material from Pontlevoy-Thenay and Artenay. Later, Ginsburg
 292 (1961) erected the genus *Hoplictis* as a subgenus of *Ischyriactis* recognizing *Ischyriactis* (*Hoplictis*)
 293 *noueli*, *Ischyriactis* (*Hoplictis*) *florancei*, and *Ischyriactis* (*Hoplictis*) *helbingi*, and subsequently raised it
 294 to generic status (Ginsburg and Morales 1992; Ginsburg 1999, 2002; Baskin 2005). The latter
 295 assignment to the genus level is followed herein.

296 There is a significant convergence in the dentitions of the large mustelids of [Central Europe](#) and
 297 Turkey during the early and middle Miocene, which is reflected by the complex systematic history
 298 described above. The dentition of the earlier species of *Hoplictis* (*H. noueli*, *H. florancei*, and *H.*
 299 *anatolicus*) from the early-middle Miocene (MN4–6) of Eurasia could easily be mistaken for those of
 300 the European *Ischyriactis* spp., particularly *I. zibethoides*, in the MN5–6, and also *Laphictis mustelinus*
 301 throughout MN4–8 (Viret, 1933; Helbing 1936; Villalta Comella and Crusafont Pairó 1943; Petter
 302 1963; Roth 1989) and those of *Iberictis* spp., (Ginsburg and Morales 1992; Valenciano et al., 2018)
 303 from the early Miocene (MN4) of western Europe. However, *Hoplictis* possesses longer P4 with a
 304 reduced protocone; more reduced M1 with a smaller metacone and a smaller lingual platform
 305 (excepting *H. anatolicus*, in which the lingual platform is not reduced); a somewhat higher m1 with a
 306 residual or even absent metaconid, and a slenderer and shorter talonid, as well as the existence of a
 307 dominant hypoconid imbricated toward the protoconid than those of these mustelids.

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The dental morphology of *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp. from Tieersihabahe, Halamagai Fm fits very well with *Hoplictis* despite its remarkably smaller size in comparison with all the species described of this genus (Figs 3 and 4). *Hoplictis baihu* share with *H. noueli* and *H. florancei*, a primitive m1 talonid within the group, which consists of a lesser buccolingual reduction of the talonid compared to those of the more derived taxa, *H. helbingi* and *H. grangerensis*, from the middle-late Miocene (Figs 3 and 4). Likewise other *Hoplictis* from MN4–6 such as *H. noueli* and *H. anatolicus* and the Halamagai mustelid still retain m1 metaconid, which is lost in *H. florancei*, *H. helbingi* and *H. grangerensis*. The presence or absence of the metaconid in the sample of *H. noueli* from Artenay is variable, being lost in some specimens housed at MNHN (J. Morales pers. comm.), which reflect the trend towards the loss of the m1 metaconid even in the early species of the genus. The Halamagai mustelid differs from *H. florancei* and *H. noueli* (Fig. 4D–I) in having a shorter p2, a lesser development of the p4 distal accessory cuspid, and a weaker m1 cingulid. It also differs from *H. anatolicus* in having a slenderer p2 and p3, a further reduced m1 metaconid and a relatively broader m1 talonid, as well as a much more reduced m2. Additionally, the more derived later forms of *Hoplictis* (*H. helbingi* see Fig. 4L–N and *H. grangerensis*) are larger and slenderer, with the m1 paraconid higher than that of the Chinese one. A direct comparison with *Hoplictis? petteri* (Crusafont-Pairó, 1972) from Can Llobateres I, Vallès-Penedès Basin, Spain, early Vallesian, MN9, is not possible because it is exclusively known by a very large and robust P4. Consequently, because of the above discussion, we erect *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp., which represents the first record of *Hoplictis* in Asia and also the smallest species of the genus. Among the earlier species of *Hoplictis*, *H. baihu* denotes a primitive species, closer to *H. florancei* and *H. noueli* than to *H. anatolicus*, but also it possesses some derived features such as a very reduced m2. However with the available remains of this taxon, it is not possible to obtain a deeper understanding of its evolutionary affinities within this genus.

Compared with Eurasiatic gulonines, *H. baihu* is smaller than *Sthenictis neimengguensis*, from the middle Miocene of the Tunggur Fm, Inner Mongolia, China (Tseng et al., 2009), and is similar in size to some Central European mustelids from early and middle Miocene (Fig. 3), such as *Dehmictis vorax* from the early Miocene, MN3, of Wintershof-West, Germany (Dehm 1950), and some primitive *Martes* from middle Miocene of Europe (see Ginsbug 1999, and Peigné 2012) (Fig. 5). The overall morphology of these ancient gulonines is very different from those of *H. baihu*. Among other features, they possess longer and slenderer lower premolars, smaller accessory cuspid in the p4; an m1 with a greater development of the metaconid, a longer, wider and more basined talonid and a more developed m2 than those of the Halamagai form. Additionally, *D. vorax* and *Martes sansaniensis* have an enlarged entocristid unlike *H. baihu* (Fig. 5D–G). *Sthenictis neimengguensis*, *D. vorax* and *M. sansaniense* have in common the presence of a relatively unreduced talonid basin, which becomes more trenchant in other hypercarnivorous mustelids such as the Holarctic *Hoplictis* spp., the Asiatic *Pycotis inamatus* Babbitt, 1999, and the African *Namibictis senuti*.

Pycotis inamatus from Hsanda Gol Fm, late Oligocene of Mongolia (Babbitt 1999), is older but more evolved than *H. baihu*, which shares a similar size and an analogous morphology of the lower molars, including a reduction of the m2. However, *H. baihu* differs in having wider p3 and p4, the occurrence of a distal accessory cuspid in p4, and in the presence of a more primitive m1. In this sense, the m1 of *H. baihu* shows a metaconid, lower paraconid and hypoconid, and a lesser basined m1 talonid than those of *P. inamatus*. Although there is a strong resemblance in size and shape between the new Chinese form and *P. inamatus*, the highly derived state of the Mongolian mustelid, and the great temporal gap between the two makes the inclusion of this new taxon in *Pycotis* unlikely. Interestingly, the remarkable convergence in the dentition of these two forms can be understood by the possession of a comparable hypercarnivorous diet in these Asiatic taxa. *Namibictis senuti* represents an additional hypercarnivorous form exclusively known by mandibular remains (Morales et al., 1998, 2003). It was described by Morales et al. (1998) based on fossils from the late early Miocene of Arrisdrift, Namibia. It is a large mustelid, which is close in morphology to *Hoplictis* spp., (Figs 4 and 5N–P). Like the former mustelids, it has a high p4, a residual m1 metaconid and a modified m1 talonid, being reduced in length and width. However, it possesses a taller distal accessory cuspid in the p4, and a more derived m1 talonid, the hypoconid of which is extremely bevelled in the lingual wall, representing the main difference between the African mustelid and *Hoplictis*.

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 362 The absence of dentition in the hemimandible V24988 (Figs 2G–I and 4J–K), assigned herein to
 363 *Hoplictis* cf. *helbingi* from Duolebulejin (Kekemaiden Fm), makes taxonomic attribution difficult. The
 364 presence of the enlarged p2, p3, a reduced m2 and the absence of the m3 exclude it from Ursidae
 365 (including hemicyonines). The m2 alveolus, albeit slightly oval in V24988, it is not as elongated and
 366 double-rooted as in [the](#) Ailuridae. The presence of p2, absence of diastema between canine and lower
 367 premolars, and the more developed alveolus of m2 than those of [the](#) Felidae exclude it from this family.
 368 The occurrence of a relatively slender p2 and p3, and relatively enlarged distal root in m1 in comparison
 369 with Hyaenidae and Percrocutidae prevent its attribution to either of these families. In this sense, the
 370 only family of carnivores to which V24988 can be assigned- is [to](#)the Mustelidae, since the enlargement
 371 and robusticity of the alveoli of the premolars and the reduction of the post-carnassial molars. The large
 372 dimensions of the hemimandible V24988, means that its inclusion in the European Miocene mustelids is
 373 unlikely notably *Iberictis* Ginsburg and Morales, 1992, *Ischyriictis*, and *Laphictis* Viret, 1933, and
 374 understandably not in *Hoplictis baihu* either (Fig. 3). Nevertheless, its size is comparable to the
 375 mandibles of some giant mustelids found in Eurasia and North America (*Eomellivora* Zdanksy, 1924,
 376 *Hoplictis* and *Plesiogulo* Zdanksy, 1924), although both *Eomellivora* and the gulonine *Plesiogulo*
 377 appear in China exclusively during the late Miocene (MN11-13) (Zdanksy 1924; Teilhard de Chardin
 378 1945; Kurtén 1970; Valenciano et al., 2015, 2018). Among these large mustelids, the mustelid from
 379 Duolebulejin could be related with the mellivorines *Eomellivora* and *Hoplictis* owing to the possession
 380 of a rotated p2 in the lower tooth row, big alveoli for the p3 and p4, enlarged and slender m1, and a
 381 slightly oval m2 alveolus. Thus, only two candidates of large mustelids within *Hoplictis* lived in Europe
 382 and North America at the same time [with](#)as the Duolebulejin mustelid, which are *H. helbingi* and *H.*
 383 *grangearensis* respectively. *Hoplictis helbingi* is a poorly known large mustelid found in [W](#)western
 384 Europe. The only described material consists of a P4 and m1 from La Grive, France, MN7–8 (Viret
 385 1951) and a fragmentary mandible with a complete m1 and both p4 and m2 alveoli from Castell de
 386 Barberà, Vallès-Penedès Basin, Spain, early late Miocene, MN9 (Crusafont-Pairó 1972) (Fig. 4L–N). It
 387 is characterized by possession of a felid-like m1, which is long and slender with a reduced talonid. The
 388 first remains from La Grive were interpreted by Depéret (1892) to be an m1 of *Aelurogale intermedia*
 389 Filhol, 1872, a saber-tooth Feliformia in the family Nimravidae a species that is currently assigned as
 390 *Nimravus intermedius* (Piveteau, 1931). Viret (1951) realised that this carnivoran from La Grive was
 391 not a Feliformia and placed it within Mustelidae.

392 The fragmented hemimandible of *H. helbingi* from Castell de Barberà (Fig. 4L–N) possesses alveoli
 393 for the p4 and m2 [since](#) the dimensions and morphology of which are practically identical to those of
 394 V24988 (Figs 2G–I, and 4J–K). Even though the ranges of variation of the teeth of *H. helbingi* and *H.*
 395 *grangearensis* are incompletely known, the size of the alveoli of the Chinese hemimandible correspond
 396 better within the range of variability of *H. helbingi* than [that](#) of the North American *H. grangearensis*
 397 (Fig. 3), in which the m1 is more robust. The m1 of *H. grangearensis* described by Edwards (1976) is
 398 more slender than the corresponding tooth in the holotype; the m1 is broken and worn, so it is not useful
 399 for comparison. Hence, we attribute the edentulous hemimandible V24988 to *Hoplictis* cf. *helbingi*,
 400 presumably representing the first record of *Hoplictis helbingi* outside Western Europe. However, more
 401 material is necessary in order to clarify the [assi](#)gnation of this specimen.

402 [Sivamellivora Kretzoi, 1942 was created based on a complete m1 \(GSI No. 243: holotype\) and a few](#)
 403 [lower premolars described as *Mellivora* \(?\) *necrophila* Pilgrim, 1932 from the Lower Siwaliks \(India\),](#)
 404 [Chinji formation ca. 14-11.2 Ma \(Patnaik, 2013\). Posteriorly, it was assigned to *Ischyriictis* \(*Hoplictis*\)](#)
 405 [*necrophila* by Schmidt-Kittler \(1976\) and finally determined as *Hoplictis necrophila* by Petter \(1987\)](#)
 406 [\(Bonis et al., 2009\). Recently Bonis et al. \(2009: p 46\) stated *Hoplictis* and *Sivamellivora* are synonyms](#)
 407 [with priority to the Siwalik one. In any case, if this proposal is valid, it would not affect the whole](#)
 408 [genus, but rather the most derived form such as *Hoplictis helbingi* and *H. grangerensis* which are closer](#)
 409 [in size and morphology to the Siwaliks species \(Fig. 3\). However, the premolars of *S. necrophila* show a](#)
 410 [primitive pattern that is what led Kretzoi \(1942\) to create a distinctive genus separating it from similar](#)
 411 [forms. Thus, more material of *S. necrophila* is needed to evaluate that hypothesis.](#)

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413 A third species of a very large *Hoplictis* was described from Can Llobateres I, early Vallesian, MN9,
 414 Vallès-Penedès Basin, Spain, as *Hoplictis petteri* (Crusafont-Pairó, 1972), represented by a large and
 415 robust P4. However, based on the only two available P4 of *Hoplictis* (*H. helbingi* and *H. anatolicus* see
 416 Viret, 1951 and Schmidt-Kittler, 1976 respectively), the attribution of this mustelid to this genus is
 417 doubtful. Its morphology is closer to the early late Miocene, MN9, *Eomellivora* (= *Hadriactis*) *fricki* (Pia,
 418 1939) from Austria (Pia 1939; Zapfe 1948; Valenciano et al., 2017). The tooth from Can Llobateres I is
 419 close morphologically and has similar dimensions to the P4 of *E. fricki* (NHMW 2016/0065/0001)
 420 (Valenciano et al., 2017). Therefore we propose to reattribute it to *E. fricki* (= *Hoplictis petteri*),
 421 expanding increasing its paleobiogeographic distribution from Austria to the Iberian Peninsula.

422

423 5.1 Palaeobiogeographical implications

424 The earliest specimens of *Hoplictis* are recorded in Western and Central Europe during the late
 425 early Miocene (MN4) (Fig. 6) with the species *H. noueli* from Artenay and *H. florancei* from
 426 Erkertshofen 2 (Mayet 1908; Roth 1989). Later, *Hoplictis* dispersed eastwards to Turkey in the early
 427 middle Miocene (MN5–6) with *H. anatolicus* and to the North-West of China in the late Shanwangian –
 428 early Tunggurian or MN5–6 with *H. baihu*. The phylogenetic relationships of *H. baihu* are uncertain,
 429 but based on its primitive status and some shared features with the European species *H. noueli* and *H.*
 430 *florancei*, it could indicate a possible Western or Central European affinity. The occurrence for the first
 431 time of *Hoplictis* in Asia is coherent with the dispersion event registered previously from Europe to
 432 North America via Asia (Qiu 2003; Baskin 1998, 2005). This event has been proved recently with
 433 amphicyonids from Halamagai Fm (Jiangzuo et al., 2018) and supports a Palaeartic Neogene faunal
 434 exchange of carnivorans between Europe and Asia during the early middle Miocene.

435 At the end of the middle Miocene the largest species of the genus appeared. *Hoplictis helbingi* has
 436 been recorded in Western Europe throughout the middle Miocene and early late Miocene (c. MN7–9)
 437 and the genus subsequently migrated towards North America during the early late Miocene (Fig. 6). The
 438 presence of *H. cf. helbingi* in China could suggest that *Hoplictis* migrated from Europe to North
 439 America, through Northwest of China during the late Tunggurian, equivalent to MN7–8 in Europe,
 440 where *H. grangearensis* evolved in the North American continent in the late Clarendonian.
 441 Nevertheless, the absence of dentition in the described mandible of *H. cf. helbingi* makes it impossible
 442 to verify such a hypothesis, nor to make a direct comparison between *H. helbingi* and *H. grangerensis*.
 443 Nonetheless, the occurrence in Asia of these two species of *Hoplictis*, emphasizes the importance of the
 444 study of the mustelids and other carnivores of the middle Miocene of Northwest China, in order to
 445 increase our understanding of these faunas.

446

447 6 Conclusions

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449 We describe a new species of *Hoplictis* (*Hoplictis baihu* n. sp.) from Tieersihabahe (Halamagai Fm),
 450 and the presence of a second species of the same genus from Duolebulejin (Kekemaideng Fm),
 451 provisionally attributed to *H. cf. helbingi*, from the middle Miocene of Halamagai and Kekemaideng
 452 Fms in Ulungur River area, Xinjiang, north-western China. These new mustelids represent the first
 453 undoubted remains of mustelids reported in the Halamagai Fm and the first record of Carnivora in the
 454 Kekemaiden Fm. Similarly, they denote the first occurrence of *Hoplictis* in East Asia, thereby greatly
 455 expanding the known distribution and diversity of the genus. *Hoplictis baihu* is the smallest recognised
 456 species of *Hoplictis*. It is coeval with *H. florancei* and *H. anatolicus*, but is different enough to warrant
 457 erection of a distinct species. The large edentulous mandible from Duolebulejin (Kekemaiden Fm) is
 458 attributed to *H. cf. helbingi*. It is related to the large-sized lineage of *Hoplictis* from the late middle
 459 Miocene, and could represent the first record of *H. helbingi* outside Western Europe. Thus, the
 460 occurrence in Asia of these two species of *Hoplictis*, supports a Palaeartic Neogene dispersal event of
 461 carnivorans between Europe and Asia during the late Shanwangian – early Tunggurian corresponding to
 462 MN5–6 in Europe, as well as another dispersion event from Europe to North America, via Northwest
 463 China during the late Tunggurian, equivalent to MN7–8 in Europe.

464

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the following curators and collection managers for access to comparative material under their care: J. Chen, H. Si and H. Chen (IVPP), M. March and J. Galindo (ICP). We further thank Loic Costeur (NMB) for the pictures of *Hoplictis noueli* from Artenay housed at NBM, Serdar Mayda (Ege University) for the pictures of *Hoplictis florancei* from Erkertshofen 2 and *Dehmictis vorax* from Wintershof-West, and Jorge Morales (MNCN) for the measurements of *Hoplictis noueli* from Artenay and *Hoplictis florancei* from Pontlevoy, as well as pictures from *Martes sansaniensis* from Sansan. We also thank J.M. Robles and D. M. Alba (ICP) for their assistance with the ICP collections. We would also like to thank the people who participated in the fieldwork in the Ulungur River area, S. Xu and C. Suo. The current work was supported by Chinese Academy of Sciences (Grant Nos. XDA20070203, XDB26000000, QYZDY-SSW-DQC-22, GJHZ1885), the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant Nos. 41430102 and 41772018, 41625005). The support of the DST-NFR Centre of Excellence in Palaeosciences (CoE-Pal) toward this research for A. Valenciano (COE2018-09POST) is hereby acknowledged. Opinions expressed and conclusions arrived at, are those of the author and are not necessarily to be attributed to the CoE. Finally we thank Martin Pickford for improving the English. We are also indebted to the Scientific Editor Lian Liu, the Editor-in-Chief Degan Shu and two anonymous reviewers for their useful comments and suggestions, which improved the original manuscript.

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690 About the first author

691 VALENCIANO Alberto, is a Spanish Ph.D. specialist in faunas of carnivorans from the Neogene of
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695 paleobiology, aiming on the evolution of the mustelids, mephitids, ailurids, canids, amphicyonids, and
696 ursids, with special attention to the Faunas of Spain, Turkey, China and South Africa. He also studies
697 another Neogene families as felids, herpestids and viverrids from the same regions.

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699
700 **Table 1 Measurements (mm) of mustelid teeth from Ulungur River area. Abbreviation: EL, external length;**
701 **IL, internal length; L, length; W, width; PL, paraconid length; AW, anterior (trigonid) width; PW, posterior**
702 **(talonid) width; TrL, trigonid length; TrH, trigonid height.**

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705 Fig 1. Map localizing the fossil sites in the Halamagai and Kekemaideng formations, such as the type localities of
706 *Hoplictis* spp.

707 Fig 2. New fossil material of *Hoplictis* from the Halamagai and Kekemaideng formations, (middle Miocene,

China). (a–c), *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp., left hemimandible, V24986 (holotype) from Halamagai. (a), buccal view, (b), Lingual view, (c), occlusal view; (d–f), *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp., partial left hemimandible, V25014 from Halamagai. (d), buccal view, (e), lingual view, (f), occlusal view; (g–i), *Hoplictis cf. helbingi*, partial right hemimandible, V24988 from Duolebulejin (Kekemaideng Fm). (g), buccal view, (h), lingual view, (i), occlusal view.

Fig 3. Measurements (mm) of the lower dentition of *Hoplictis* spp., *Ischyriactis* spp., *Iberictis* spp., *Laphictis mustelinus*, *Sivamellivora necrophila*, *Pyctis inamatus*, *Dehmictis vorax* depicted by bivariate plots of bucco-lingual width (W) vs. mesio-distal length (L). (a), p4; (b), m1. * means the type locality of each species. Sources: Mayet, 1908; Pilgrim, 1932; Viret, 1933; Helbing, 1936; Dehm, 1950; Viret, 1951; Mein, 1958; Bryant, 1968; Crusafont-Pairó, 1972; Edwards, 1976; Schmidt-Kittler, 1976; Roth, 1989; Ginsburg and Morales, 1992; Morales et al., 1998; Babbitt, 1999; Baskin, 2005; Nagel et al., 2009; Tseng et al., 2009; Peigné, 2012.

Fig 4. Mandibles of species of *Hoplictis* considered in this manuscript. (a–c), *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp., left hemimandible, V24986 (holotype) from Tiersihabahe (Halamagai Fm). (a), buccal view, (b), lingual view, (c), occlusal view; (d–f), *Hoplictis florancei* (type species), partial left hemimandible BSPG 1974- XIV- 1032 from Erkerthshofen 2, MN4. (d), buccal view, (e), lingual view, (f), occlusal view; (g–i), *Hoplictis noueli*, partial left hemimandible NMB SO31 from Artenay, MN4. (g), Buccal view, (h), lingual view, (i), Occlusal view; (j–k), *Hoplictis aff. helbingi*, partial right hemimandible, V24988 from Duolebulejin (Kekemaideng Fm). (j), buccal view, (k), occlusal view; (l–n), *Hoplictis helbingi*, partial left hemimandible IPS33185 from Castell de Barberà, MN9. (l), buccal view, (m), lingual view, (n), occlusal view.

Fig 5. *Hoplictis baihu* and main comparative lower dentitions of middle Miocene small to medium sized mustelids from Europe and Africa considered in this [workmanuscript](#). (a–c), *Hoplictis baihu* n. sp., left hemimandible, V24986 (holotype) from Tiersihabahe (Halamagai Fm). (a), buccal view, (b), lingual view, (c), occlusal view; (d), *Dehmictis vorax*, right hemimandible, BSPG 1937-II-13290 from Wintershof-West, Germany, lingual view; (e–g), *Martes sansaniensis*, right m1, MNHN Sa962 from Sansan, France, MN6. (e), buccal view, (f), lingual view, (g), occlusal view; (h–j), *Martes munki*, cast of right m1 housed at MNCN, from La Grive MN7–8. (h), buccal view, (i), lingual view, (j) occlusal view; (k–m), *Martes burdigaliensis*, left m1, cast of the holotype housed at MNCN, from Vieux-Collonges, France MN5. (k), buccal view, (l), lingual view, (m), occlusal view; (n–p), *Namibictis senuti*, right hemimandible, AD 529'99 from Arrisdrift, Namibia, middle Miocene. (n), buccal view, (o), lingual view, (p), occlusal view.

Fig 6. Chronostratigraphic position of species of *Hoplictis*. The arrows indicate dispersion events. Chronostratigraphical and biochronological correlations of North American land mammal age (NALMA) based on a Tedford et al. (2004), Albright et al. (2008), and Hilgen et al. (2012); European Mammal Neogene Units (MN) based on Hilgen et al. (2012). Stratigraphic ranges of the taxa based on Mayet (1908), Viret (1951), Bryant, (1968), Crusafont-Pairó (1972), Edwards (1976), Schmidt-Kittler (1976), Roth (1989), Gürbüz (1992), Baskin (2005) and this manuscript. Abbreviations: Ar4, Arikarean 4; ELMA, European land mammal ages; NALMA, North American land mammal ages (units defined by immigrant taxa).

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170x163mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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	p2	L	W	W/L			
V24986	(alveolus)	4.42	2.38				
V25014		5.32	2.72	0.51			
V24988	(alveolus)	10.10	5.52				
	p3	L	W	W/L			
V24986		5.46	3.22	0.59			
V25014		5.38					
V24988	(alveolus)	11.42	6.18				
	p4	L	W	W/L	Lp4/Lm1		
V24986		7.12	3.72	0.52	0.65		
V25014		7.52	3.52	0.47	0.54		
V24988	(alveolus)	13.88	7.46		0.68		
	m1	L	PL	AW	TrL	PW	TrH
V24986		11.02	4.42	4.48	8.58	3.72	7.02
V24988	(alveolus)	20.28		6.62			
	m2	L	W	W/L	Lm2/Lm1		
V24986		2.62	2.58	0.98	0.24		
V24988	(alveolus)	7.00	5.12		0.35		
	mandible	height p2	width p2	height m1	width m1	w/h p2	w/h m1
V24986		12.68	8.12	13.48	6.82	0.64	0.51
V24988		23.82	10.82	27.32	10.78	0.45	0.39